

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B359
Date: 23 April 2008
Take Off: 08:21:41Z
Landing: 10:45:52Z
Flight Time 2h 24

Campaign: ACAS

Operating Area: Rotterdam – North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Trainer 1	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
9	Trainer 2	Steve Devereau	FAAM
10	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office
11	ACAS Training	Wiebke Frey	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz
12	ACAS Training	Kostas Markakis	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
13	ACAS Training	Matthew Blackett	Kings College
14	ACAS Training	Cedric Chou	ETH Zurich
15	ACAS Training	Beata Takacs	Institute of Geography, Hungary
16	ACAS Training	Ana Calvo	University of Leon, Spain

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B359
 Date: 23 April 2008
 Project: ACAS
 Location: Rotterdam to East Anglia

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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073902		Start-Up	-.08 kft	326	51'56.98N, 4'26.15E
081923		ASP	-.08 kft	326	Open
082141		T/O	1.2 kft	068	Rotterdam
083105		Video	3.0 kft	262	Start FFC & DFC1
083236	083541	Profile 1	3.0 - 1.5 kft	302	1.5k',500fpm, QNH 1015hPa
083541	084557	Run 1	1.5 kft	303	
084557	084830	Profile 2	1.5 - -.01 kft	301	1.5k'-50'
084831	084935	Profile 3	-.01 - 0.44 kft	309	50'-500'
084955	085941	Run 2	0.46 kft	304	500'
085645		Event	0.48 kft	316	Heimann cal
090013	091015	Run 2.2	0.44 - 0.56 kft	264	Perpendicular to wind
090318		Event	0.43 kft	267	Ship plume
090848		Event	0.44 kft	270	O3 and CO event
091157	091257	Profile 4	0.45 - 0.00 kft	089	500-50', 500fpm
091306	091442	Profile 5	0.05 - 1.5 kft	097	50'-1.5k',1000fpm
091454	092709	Profile 5	1.5 - 14.0 kft	087	
091743		Event	4.6 kft	087	Cloud base 4k'
092851	094547	Profile 5	14.0 - 33.0 kft	254	
093133		Event	18.8 kft	242	Zero Nevzorov
094223		Event	31.2 kft	261	Contrailling
094734		Event	33.0 kft	038	Zero JW & Nevz
094809	095240	Run 3	33.0 kft	076	Above Cirrus
095445	095847	Run 4	30.1 - 30.0 kft	256	Below Cirrus
095550		Event	30.0 kft	265	Zero JW & Nevz
100054	100611	Run 5.1	31.0 kft	075	In Cirrus
100337		Video	31.0 kft	087	Change Tapes
100345		Sonde	31.0 kft	087	Launch #01
100629	100952	Run 5.2	31.0 kft	086	Patchy Cirrus
103407	103931	Profile 6	4.8 - 2.0 kft	140	500fpm
104552		Land	-.09 kft	138	Rotterdam
104653		ASP	-.09 kft	237	Close
105023		Shutdown	-.09 kft	326	51'56.98N, 4'26.15E

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B359 Track 23-APR-08

Sortie brief – ACAS summer school

Flight B: B359

Mission scientist: Dave Kindred

Briefing: 7:15 LT

Take off: 10:30 LT

Land: 12:50 LT

Aim: To examine the response of aerosol-plumes from Europe to changes in boundary layer stability. To examine the relationship between aerosol and cloud particle concentrations in cirrus cloud layers.

Location: S. North Sea (Area D)

Weather conditions: Approaching frontal system from the west. Southeasterly flow from central Europe.

Key instruments: Aerosol and cloud particle counters and:

- Johnson Williams, Nevzorov – ensure zero calibration when level in cloud-free air
- CVI – aerosol mode when out of cloud, CVI mode in cloud,
- PSAP, TWC evaporator

Sortie brief:

1. Transit into UK airspace as much as possible with wind direction including one dip to 50ft (1500 ft) (25 mins)
2. Turn perpendicular to plume/wind (10 mins)
3. Dip perpendicular to plume/wind and profile climb to top of boundary layer (15 mins)
4. Climb to FL 300 (15 mins)
5. 4 runs one below cirrus two in cirrus and one above cirrus (40mins)
6. in final run drop dropsonde
7. RTB (30 mins)

MISSION SCIENTIST DEBRIEFING SHEET

Date: Wednesday 23rd April 2008

Flight Number: B359

Overall, a successful sortie – both from the science aims & objectives realised, and as a Training and Education exercise for the 6 ACAS students onboard.

After T/O from Rotterdam airport at 0822z, we transited at 3000 ft SW until over the coast, letting down to 1500 ft for a S&L run through the v. hazy and heavily polluted airmass over the southern N.Sea until the FIR/UK airspace boundary. We then profiled down to 50 ft, followed by a profile ascent to 500 ft, for another S&L run NW'wards towards N. Norfolk, to measure aerosol (and ship plume/smoke) from a lower level.

Next, we profiled again down to 50 ft, and then made a 'deep' profile (initially at 500 ft/min through the Boundary Layer, followed by 1000 ft/min above the haze/pollution and Cu/Sc cloud tops ie from about 7000 ft) up to FL 330 (Profile P5). A rather thin and patchy upper cloud Ci layer was then 'worked' (at FL330 above, FL300 below, and FL310 through the ice-cloud), each for about 4 minutes, flying E-W runs over Norfolk The final leg was extended by about 3 minutes, where also a dropsonde was launched - good met data & winds were provided all the way down to the surface.

Finally, recovery back to Rotterdam included a final profile (P6 - 6000 ft down to 2000 ft) once again through the heavily polluted air-mass.

Winds were generally S.E. over Holland, becoming more S'ly over the southern N.Sea and East Anglia (about 5-10 kts at low level, around 30 kts at high levels). Visibility was poor, sometimes very poor within the haze/pollution layer up to about 5000 ft (being topped by the Cu/Sc cloud layer). Otherwise, clouds were tending to thicken and lower as we headed towards the approaching frontal system (ie to the W of the operating area), especially at high levels (Ci/Cs cloud), and also including thin, patchy medium-level layers of Ac cloud.

An interesting flight, with many and varying meteorological conditions to fly through and capture data from. B359 should provide an excellent dataset for these E&T students (no significant instrument problems were encountered). Sortie timing was 2 h 24 min – 4 minutes longer than estimated from the sortie brief.

DRK
24/04/08

4/11/2008

ACAS (KULAR). FLIGHT 2.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B359** Date **23/4/08** Name **DR KUNDREDDY** Page **1** of **3**
 (WEDC)

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0815			→		START TAXI. (QNH = 1015).
0822					T/O ROTTERDAM (RW 06) V. hazy/polluted low level, otherwise SKY CLEAR ahead (to E)
0825		3000'	SW		
0828					Passing over Rotterdam port No cloud above.
083236	P1 3000' ↓	3000'	302°	S ₁ 54°N E ₁ 42°W	Start Profile P1 at wind 165/10kt Still in polluted layer @ 500'/min. Some Ac (2/8) above; Some Ci ahead.
083541	END P1/START R1	1500'	302°		Run @ 1500' measuring aerosol/pollution Siting/significant P1 on C-Physics (PCASP).
084557	START P2 P2 ↓	1500'	301°		Start P2 ↓ 1500' to 500' @ 500'/min
084831	P2 ↓ P3 ↑	50'	307°	S ₂ 30°N E ₂ 24°E	End P2 at 50' & start P3 ↑ to 500'.
084935	END P3 START R2	500'	304°		End P2 at 500', start R2 ↓ 2 min W wards. Conc ⁿ at 500' : 300 on PCASP * VISUALLY 'THICK HAZE' HERE STILL (lower values yesterday).
0851			→		Nox 60, HD2 ~ 30 : CO instrument rebooted.
085941	END R2.1	500'			END R2.1 at 500'. Turning ↗ onto 270°.
090013	R2.2	500'	266°	S ₃ 00°N E ₃ 30°E	START R2.2 ↓ 500' - wind 145°/8-10kt ↓ for to plane/wind [A/c wind 180°/10kt]
090315-20			→		Passing cargo vessel (med size) to port. Nothing seen(↑) on C-Physics
090630 → 090700					(+200ft in NCH values!) O3 ↑, CO ↓ q. markedly.
0907			→		Will turn onto E for P3 Sertie Brief
091015	END R2.2	500'	265°		END R2.2 & ↘ onto 090°.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B359** Date 23/4/08 Name DLK Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
091115					Co ↑ in turn; O ₃ little change.
091157	START P4 ↓	500'	091°		Start P4 ↓ 50' @ 500'/min.
091306	END P4 / START PS	50			End P4 @ 50'; climb to above 1000'/min. BL (~6000').
091442			→		Interrupt PS ↑.
091454			→		Resume PS.
091618		Passing 3000'	087°		Cloud at ~4000' (capping top of BL)
091836			→		Passing thro' Cu now.
0920		~7000'			Top of cloud (Cu/Sc above BL)
					Continue with profile PS up to FL 300.
092315	PS	11,200'	105°		Have got patches of Ci above !!
092709	PS ↑	FL 40			Interrupt PS & turn ↓.
092851	PS ↑	FL 140	257°		Resume PS ↑ (Heading further W [turns & change to 150°] for Ci - thicker here)
094330		31900'	→		Climb to ~ FL 330
094547	END PS	FL 330	262°	52° 30' N 0° 00' E	End PS at FL 330 Turning onto 090°.
					* WILL NOW WORK Ci IN THIS AREA *
					* TIME ONLY FOR 1 RUN ABOVE, 1 IN & 1 BELOW (4 mins each) *
094809	START RUN 3	FL 330	088°		Start RUN 3 WIND 185°/30kt.
095155			→		OA Temp -55°C.
095240	END RUN 3	FL 330			End R3; Turn & descend to FL 300 onto reciprocal.
095445	START R4	FL 300			Start R4 (Should be 'in' cloud but seems to be underneath (visually & on CI. Physics) (reciprocal))
					So THIS IS ^{Now} UNDER CLOUD RUN
095847	END R4	FL 300	266°		End R4 Turning & climb to FL 315 for in Ci RUN (hopefully) at this height
100054	START R5	FL 310	084°		Start R5 at FL 310

1. Pollution/Haze surface → 7000'
2. Ci layer (See/c. Phys)
3. Atm. Temp/Hum. profile

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B359** Date **28/4/08** Name **DLK** Page **3** of **3**.

GMT	Run/Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100230		→			Continued from previous R band run (FL330) clearly seen above & to port.
100345		→			Side #1 DEP
	END	*Thicker (c. Phys)	Ci at beginning of this run.*		Still continuing in this run
100629	S.1 / S.2	FL310	087°		with End RS.1 / Start RS.2 (Extended run at FL310 on return to Rotterdam).
100958					Under Ci now End RS.2, Descend to FL270
100952	END RS.2	FL310			
		* END of SCIENCE			(but see PG below) for Air Traffic restrictions
101120		→			5-6/c Ci above (thin) + contrails layers Ac/Sc below 6/c (to SW) - (less to East) - & Cu/Sc layer with haze/pollution layer below to E of AC
101507					Hope Now LANDED; Good Met + Wind data on descent. ATC routing necessitated 'loop' over NE Norfolk, before being given clearance to RTB.
<u>Instrument Status:</u>		CWI - Working for Ci runs OK, problems before this.			
		C. Chem - Co needed reboiling (x1), otherwise fine			
		C. Phys/Secs - OK, SID 2 noisy, sync			
		ANAPS - ✓ OK.			
		[NEWS] -			
		FLT MAN - GIN (1° S of present pos ⁿ ; Restarted on Taxi). OK thereafter.			
* MET	CONDITIONS	LOOKING S/SE Towards + Haze/Pollution up to ~6000' (small Cu above)			
103407	START PG.	~6000'	DUTCH Coast SE.		's PG 2500/min thro Pollution layer (v. murky conditions on descend!)
103931	END PG	2000'	→		END PG & prepare to approach/land.
1046		→			LAND ROTTERDAM. (2W06)

0822
0242

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B359

Date: 23/04/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:33:00	1600	0.11	3		10											Start Profile 1 from 3000'	
08:34:25	1700	0.11			10											2000'	
08:36:00	1500	0.11		5	10											End of Profile 1 & Start run 1	
08:38:00	1600	0.11	4	5	7												
08:40:00	1450	0.12		5	8												
08:42:00	1170	0.12		5	5												
08:44:00	1690	0.11		5	5												
08:46:04																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 2	
08:46:45	2310	0.12	5	5	10											1000'	
08:48:30	2750	0.10		5	10											End of Profile 2 & Start Profile 3 @ 50'	
08:49:40																500'	
08:50:00	3600	0.10	6	10	10												
08:52:00	3000	0.10		10	10												
08:54:00	3000	0.10		10	10												
08:56:00	2950	0.10	7	10	10												
08:58:00	3200	0.10		10	10												
8:59:41																End of Run	
09:00:13																Start Run 2.2	
09:01:00	3300	0.10	8	10	10												
09:03:00	2790	0.10		10	10												
09:05:00	2900	0.10	9	10	10												
09:07:00	2200	0.10		10	10												
09:09:00	2700	0.09	10	10	10												
09:10:14																End of Run 2.2	
09:12:05																Start Profile 3 from 500'	
09:12:56	3400	0.09	11	10	10											End of Profile 3 & Start Profile 4 @ 50'	
09:14:30	1300	0.11		10	10											1500'	
09:16:15	1150	0.13	12	1	20											FLK030	
09:17:13	1200	0.16	230	2000	5000											FL040	
09:18:25	700	0.11	341	20	1000											FL050	
09:19:17	380	0.10		10	10											FL060	
09:20:13	110	0.09	395													FL070	
09:21:04	90	0.08														FL080	
09:22:05	80	0.08														FL090	
09:23:15	30	0.10														FL100	
09:24:06	35	0.09														FL110	
09:25:09	45	0.09														FL120	
09:26:58	30	0.09														FL140	
09:31:10	4	0.15	396	1	1											FL180	
09:32:10	10	0.07		1	1											FL200	
09:33:20	6	0.07		1	1											FL220	
09:34:50	3	0.07		1	1											FL240	
09:36:20	5	0.07		1	1											FL260	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.0V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.2V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.8 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 22 mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.0V		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of flight:

T/O: 082141
Land: 104552

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = 07,08,09,10 Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	070000 105959	Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Ffssp_cal28022008.txt Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized? okay

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat = 321087
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 50152 Blocks written = 50152 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y Y Y Y Y N N	Start = 0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 0 End = 240000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =0 End = 240000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 1157.679 SECONDS 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat Y</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

b359_cvi_log & b359_cvi_log2

4/23/08 8:27:58 AM pcasp error on firsdtd startup - restart and now ok
4/23/08 8:28:03 AM horace feed ok
4/23/08 8:28:12 AM cpc ok high conc
4/23/08 8:28:51 AM problem on b358 where t-tip >200 two hundred deg c!!!!
4/23/08 8:31:58 AM justfound hand tap on cvi filter unit, now turned to OFF and cvi filter has now just dropped to -0.17 l/min
4/23/08 8:32:18 AM vac pump is off
4/23/08 8:33:16 AM CVI will be in aerosol mode for the start of the flight, ie take off and transit over to UK airspace
4/23/08 8:36:51 AM vacuum pump turned ON
4/23/08 8:36:57 AM prep for 1
4/23/08 8:36:58 AM prep for 1
4/23/08 8:37:07 AM prep for lyman zero
4/23/08 8:40:43 AM lyman zero
4/23/08 8:56:27 AM lyman zero again
4/23/08 8:56:36 AM remove lyman from reference flow
4/23/08 8:59:01 AM very long time lag
4/23/08 8:59:13 AM from pressure pump of to readings increasing
4/23/08 9:02:54 AM pcasp flow is slighty high on ground, so it should be very close to optimum at 1500ft for the transit
4/23/08 9:03:36 AM pressure pump on until just before take off
4/23/08 9:08:41 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:23:55 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:24:05 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:25:18 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:30:40 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:37:59 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:38:03 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:38:11 AM lip closed for take off
4/23/08 10:40:42 AM alter pcasp flows
4/23/08 10:42:28 AM presure pump on, 2d seeing small ice
4/23/08 10:43:27 AM presure pump on, 2d seeing small ice

4/23/08 10:48:17 AM restart of cvi due to shut down (operator error)
4/23/08 10:53:51 AM cvi into cloud mode start of run 4 FL300
4/23/08 10:55:03 AM Just below cloud
4/23/08 10:56:45 AM next run in cloud? trying at fl315
4/23/08 10:57:15 AM into aerosol for last part of run to try for some below cloud aerosol
4/23/08 10:58:10 AM into aerosol for last part of run to try for some below cloud aerosol
4/23/08 10:58:24 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:07:28 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:07:35 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:11:46 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:11:50 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:11:56 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:12:03 AM L control to 2.2, hopefully see some cloud ice
4/23/08 11:27:17 AM no cloud on descent so leave in aerosol mode
4/23/08 11:51:16 AM landed
4/23/08 11:53:45 AM zero'ing lyman

Flight:

B359

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B359

Date: 23 April 2008

Instruments

1. GIN – Latitude -1 degree error on start-up. Reset power then okay.
2. CO – Okay after take-off but then no data after 1st calibration. Possibly knocked pump switch off. Reboot then okay.
3. CVI – okay most of flight, accidentally switched it off but it was back on before Cirrus run.
4. Core Chem – okay apart from problem with CO (see 2.)
5. Cloud Physics – all okay initially. SID 2 noisy later in flight and 2DC & 2DP noisy on transit return (due to cold, -38C and weak lasers), so slow data rate.
6. AVAPS (Dropsonde) – worked well, will send data to Met Office Databank

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

1 from DFL to aircraft

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 23/04/08

Flight No: B 359

Pre-Flighter: MS, SCB, PDR, DHA

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	<i>Not fitted</i>
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<i>No picture</i>
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Flight B359 09:48:00

Heading 69 deg Speed 365 knots Height 33.0kft Press 261mb

Lat 52°36.0'N Long 0°0.0'E Wind 19 ms-1/ 176 deg

Temp -55.03C Dewpoint -54.18C

From 09:14:56 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	261.73	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-55.03	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-54.19	deg C

Flight B359 10:52:24
 Heading 326 deg Speed 5 knots Height 0.0kft Press 1016mb
 Lat 51°54.0'N Long 4°24.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 295 deg
 Temp 16.78C Dewpoint 8.72C
 From 10:22:46 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 39144 secs All SC
 — OZONE MIXING RATIO -0.54 ppb
 — CO MIXING RATIO 0.87 ppb

Flight B359 10:47:20
 Heading 237 deg Speed 25 knots Height 0.0kft Press 1016mb
 Lat 51°54.0'N Long 4°24.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 201 deg
 Temp 16.6C Dewpoint 10.22C
 From 10:20:41 to now

Current values
 ++++ STATIC PRESSURE 1016.62 mb
 ++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 16.61 deg C
 ++++ DEW POINT 10.22 deg C

Flight B359 10:48:25
 Heading 207 deg Speed 21 knots Height 0.0kft Press 1016mb
 Lat 51°54.0'N Long 4°24.0'E Wind 5 ms-1/ 210 deg
 Temp 16.3C Dewpoint 9.89C
 From 10:24:54 to now

Current values
 ++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT -26.82 m All
 ++++ NEPH BLUE SP 251.54 m-1
 ++++ NEPH GREEN SP 186.09 m-1
 ++++ NEPH RED SP 128.35 m-1

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B359:

Log	Reason
Flight Manager's Instrument Status log	No log available until database entries completed
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 May 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080423_b359_081128_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080423_b359_091128_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080423_b359_101128_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080423_b359_081121_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080423_b359_091121_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080423_b359_101121_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080423_b359_081117_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080423_b359_091117_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080423_b359_101117_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080423_b359_081124_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080423_b359_091124_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080423_b359_101124_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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